

Parents' Perceptions Towards Involvement in Education of Learners with Autism Spectrum Disorder in Eswatini Mainstream Primary Schools

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 01,2023</p> <p>Accepted: November 01,2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Academic Performance, Learners With Autism, Mainstream School, Parent, Teacher</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10063523</p>	<p><i>Although in 2010 the Eswatini introduced inclusive education across all levels of the education sector, vital statistics about learners with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) remain unknown. Hence, parents of these learners remain an untapped source. This qualitative, phenomenological and interpretivism study explored parents' perceptions towards their involvement in education of learners with ASD in Eswatini mainstream primary schools. Data were collected utilising interviews and document analysis from fifteen purposively sampled parents and teachers of learners with ASD who were selected from four mainstream primary schools. Data were analysed using the six basic steps of thematic analysis as postulated by Braun and Clarke (2006). The study adhered to informed consent, self-determination, voluntary participation, anonymity and confidentiality of information. Findings revealed that mainstream primary schools offered parents minimal support. Thus, the study recommended that the Ministry of Education and Training should intensively invest in pre- and in-service training so that teachers can be adequately equipped with pivotal skills to facilitate parental involvement and collaboration with a multi-disciplinary team to enhance parental involvement.</i></p>

Introduction

Parents assume the role of being primary teachers of their children at conception stage, and this role renders them experts in catering for their children's needs (Sedibe & Fourie, 2018). In 1994, numerous countries across the globe signed the Salamanca Statement and Framework for Action on Special Needs Education, a treaty which mandates a worldwide paradigm shift towards inclusive education (Morelle & Tabane, 2019). Hence, in compliance to this international educational reform, in 2010, the Eswatini Ministry of Education and Training introduced inclusive education, as per the dictates of the Draft Inclusive Education Policy (Ministry of Education and Training, 2008). Inclusive education guarantees learners with special education needs access to education in schools in their neighbourhood, thus, according them the comfort of staying with their families (McKenzie, Shada & Aldersey, 2020). Disappointingly, in Eswatini, learners with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) have high grade repetition rate, and resultantly, a relatively high proportion of them drop-out before enrolling for secondary education (Ministry of Education and Training, 2018). Moreover, Thwala (2018) claims that unless there is additional support to the teachers, the learners cannot attain academic excellence.

The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition defines ASD as a neurodevelopmental, biologically determined disorder characterised by a triad of impairments which involve social interactions, communication skills and imagination (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). This behaviour limits the learners' help-seeking skills, and hinders the learners from successfully making personal adjustments (Dijkhuis *et al.*, 2020), thus, it adversely interferes with their learning (Zucker, 2020).

Kasongole and Muzata (2020) draw our attention to note that giving learners some work to take home for practice on class tasks which seemed challenging in class can enhance academic performance. Hence, mutual collaboration between the school and the home should be established, so that parents too can create stimulating environments (Tran *et al.*, 2020). However, irrespective of the considerable increase in prevalence rate which requires that all educational authorities need to be informed about the prevalence of ASD in their jurisdictions (Ozerk & Cardinal, 2020), parents of learners with ASD in Eswatini mainstream primary schools have not been adequately capacitated on how they should be involved in the education of their children.

All Eswatini citizens have a right to access education (Government of the Kingdom of Swaziland, 2005). In response to this constitutional promulgation, the Eswatini developed the National Disability Policy (2013) which is mandated to ensure mainstreaming of persons with ASD in all levels of society (Deputy Prime Minister's Office, 2013), and the Ministry of Education and Training Sector Policy (2018) which advocates for child-centered teaching and learning, characterized with active involvement of parents (Ministry of Education and Training, 2018).

Disappointingly, in spite of the massive reforms, this legislation and policy framework does not provide any clear guidelines with regard to the nature of parental involvement in the education of learners with special education needs. Worth noting is that the Annual Education Census Report (2018) is silent about the existence of learners with ASD (Ministry of Education and Education, 2018). This paucity of information on existence of learners with ASD may be the underlying reason which has made the parents to remain an untapped resource as to how they perceive their involvement, hence, that propelled us to carry out this investigation.

2. Research question

The main research question for this study was: ‘What are parents’ perceptions about their involvement in education of learners with ASD in Eswatini mainstream primary schools?’ To achieve this main research question, the following sub-research questions were used:

- a) How do parents perceive their involvement in the education of learners with ASD in Eswatini mainstream primary schools?
- b) What are the factors which impact parental involvement in the education of learners with ASD in Eswatini mainstream primary schools?

3. Research aim

The primary aim of this study was to explore and understand parents’ perceptions towards their involvement in the education of learners with ASD in Eswatini mainstream primary schools.’

4. Review of related literature

This study adopted an integrative theoretical approach, whereby Parent Development Theory (Mowder, 2005), was used as the backbone and this theory was augmented by the Bio-ecological Systems Theory (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Below we discuss each of these two theories.

4.1. Parent Development Theory (2005)

Parent Development Theory (2005) was developed by Mowder (Pickard, 2019), to give a comprehension of parenting as a complex combination of the parent’s own experiences, needs and life circumstances, in conjunction with the ever-changing needs of the developing child (Bradley, 2020). This theory was appropriate because it aligns multi-disciplinary expertise from a strong pool of diverse professionals, like therapists, teacher-counsellors, psychologists and special education teachers with parents to enhance parental involvement in education of the learners. This theory comprises of the six factors discussed below.

Bonding: This is the love and affection which parents bestow to their child (Mowder, 2005). In this study, bonding focused on how parents of learners with ASD committed themselves to offer unconditional love for the learners to benefit their learning.

Discipline: This dimension encompasses the limits which parents set for a child and how the parents respected and complied to those limits (Mowder, 2005). Thus, discipline focused on strategies which parents set for themselves and for the learners to ensure that parents had quality time to be involved in the education of the learners.

Education: Education denotes the strategies which parents use to teach and guide learners through communication and providing information (Mowder, 2005). In this study, education implies advice and guidance parents offered to the learners to help them to better carry out home works, and further improve in academic pursuit they had challenges in at school.

General Welfare and Protection: This concept indicates that parents have an obligation to meet their children’s basic needs, and always protect the children from both internal and external harm (Smritirekha & Satapathy, 2017). Hence, the study analysed the nature of provisions parents made to meet the basic needs of the learners with ASD to protect them from psychological, physical and emotional harm.

Responsivity: This factor denotes the extent to which parents are responsive to the needs of their children (Smritirekha & Satapathy, 2017). Responsivity, thus, entailed analysing how parents involved themselves to respond to needs of learners with ASD on health care services and encouraging the learners to study.

Sensitivity: Sensitivity refers to accurately perceiving what the child is trying to convey and addressing that need (Mowder, 2005). In this factor, we focused on how parents paid attention if they saw, heard and sensed that the learners with ASD were in need. The focus was also on how parents interpreted, as well as probed further to get meaning of hidden feelings portrayed by the learners with ASD.

4.2. Bio-ecological Systems Theory (1979)

The Bio-ecological Systems Theory (1979) was developed by Bronfenbrenner, and it views the environment as five nested systems namely, the micro-, meso-, exo-, macro- and chrono-systems. Below we discuss each system.

The micro-system: This first system constitutes a pattern of interpersonal relations experienced between individuals and the systems in which the individuals actively participate (Mabaso, 2020). In this system, we focused on how siblings, relatives and peer-groups collaborated with parents to enhance the parents’ involvement in the education of the learners with ASD.

The meso-system: This second system takes into account the link between two or more micro-systems, such as the interrelations between family and school (Yang, 2021). Hence, we focused on the quality of relationship

between stakeholders in the home level and the other micro-systems, to ascertain how teachers, therapists, counsellors and non-governmental organisations created a least restrictive environment to positively influence involvement of parents in the education of the learners with ASD.

The exo-system: This system incorporates the links between those settings which do not involve the child as an active participant (Brien, 2019), but may nevertheless affect what happens to the learner, for instance, the community, health services, school governing bodies, government and non-governmental organizations, parents' place of work, country's education system and various professionals who play diverse roles in the implementation of educational programmes and policies. Since academic and social support lead to better academic performance of learners (Morina & Biagiotti, 2022), focus was on how school governing bodies designed tailor-made policies to help parents of learners with ASD in mainstream primary schools to execute their role without viewing it as an unsurmountable task.

Macro-system: This most distant system encloses the micro-, meso- and exo-systems, and it consists of the wider pattern of ideology and organisation of social institutions which are common to a particular social class or culture (Brien, 2019). In this level, we focused on how the parents experienced different inherent pressures, prejudices, norms and stereotypical behaviours from the school, and how such issues were managed to create a least restrictive environment for parents to be actively involved in educating the learners.

The chrono-system: This system encapsulates the patterning of environmental events and historical context related to the development of the person (Bronfenbrenner & Morris, 2006). Thus, we focused on how perceptions of parents towards their involvement in education of the learners is embedded in and shaped by the paradigm shift to inclusive education as per the mandate of the Draft Inclusive Education Policy 2008 (Ministry of Education and Training, 2008).

4.3. Parental Involvement Framework (1994)

The study employed Parental Involvement Framework (1994), a framework in which Epstein categorises parental involvement into parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning-at-home, decision-making and collaborating with the community (Deger, 2021). This framework was ideal because it believes it promotes learning through cooperation between parents, school staff and community members (Epstein *et al.*, 2009). Below we describe each type of parental involvement.

Parenting: This involvement type includes activities which assist parents to improve home environments to be conducive for maximum acquisition of academic goals (Deger, 2021). In this parenting involvement type, we focused on means different stakeholders were doing to nurture the learning process by modifying the home environment so that parents could navigate their role successfully.

Communication: Communication is the vehicle through which information is transmitted from one individual to another (Buthelezi, 2020). Communication centres on designing effective activities for establishing meaningful communications between the home and school about school programs, events and the learners' progress (Salinas *et al.*, 2019). Hence, in this type we focused on the mode and frequency of communication which the schools used to enhance school programs, events and policies which aim to improve parent-to-teacher communication.

Volunteering: This type enlists activities for parental support to meet the educational goals of the school (Epstein & Sheldon, 2019). Hence, we looked at how the school developed volunteer programmes, and recruited parents, as well as organised how the school encouraged parents to volunteer in monetary aid, to enhance the education of the learners with ASD.

Learning-at-Home: This consists of establishing activities and information to improve parents' efficiency in assisting learners' to carry out homework (Epstein & Sheldon, 2019), as out-of-school tasks provide learners with practice on skills and content learnt at school, preparation for work to be done in school and for an extension of work commenced in school (Brien, 2019). In this type, we focused on the assistance and quality of time and assistance which parents and teachers rendered to support the learners in homework, as well as in preparing the learners for tests and examinations.

Decision-Making: This type encompasses parent advocacy and child-specific decision-making activities (Epstein & Sheldon, 2019), as well as district- or school-level decision making activities that influence all learners. Hence, we focused on how parents were involved in school committees and parents' meetings, as well as how decisions taken in these forums in relation to developing, implementing and reviewing school programmes were disseminated to enhance parental involvement.

Collaborating with the community: This involvement includes activities aimed at increasing cooperation among schools, families, organisations, community groups and agencies (Erdener & Knoeppel, 2018), by utilisation of resources and services from the community. In this type, we focused on how schools integrated the resources and services outside of the school to strengthen school programs, family practices and learning to improve parental involvement.

4.4 Review of related literature

Lyu *et al.* (2022) suggested that since parents of children with ASD experienced low self-esteem and high affiliate stigma, giant steps should be taken to improve the self-esteem of the entire family functioning. Leadbitter *et al.* (2020) reported that parents' involvement in therapy strengthened parents' relationship with their child and this was evident through increased attunement with and even love for their child. However, while therapy has been proven to be an essentially significant intervention for most learners with ASD, the high charges impede most parents from accessing it (Voss *et al.*, 2019).

Avnet *et al.* (2019) argue that increasing the involvement of parents in school programmes and activities provides connections to support learning in and outside the classroom. In the same light, Mowder (2005) purports that school-family relationships with an exchange of knowledge and respect, optimises means of involving parents in their children's education. Moreover, Marais (2020) established that being involved in the learners' education helped parents to better understand what was expected of them in regards to assisting the learners with ASD in their education.

Yaacob *et al.* (2021) view caring for a learner with ASD as an emotionally exhausting task which interferes with the parents' effort in helping the learner with studies, hence, a need for provision of support to sustain the parents' mental stability. Even though Amponsah *et al.* (2018) demonstrate a significant positive relationship between parents' active involvement in school and optimal acquisition of academic achievement, it is paramount to consider that poor executive functioning compromises the learners' performance in academics (McLeod, Meanwell & Hawbaker, 2019). Hence, when teaching the learners with ASD, it is essentially significant that teachers should employ tailor-made teaching strategies and methods (Sulaimani & Gut, 2019).

5. Research Method

This study lied in the utilization of a qualitative research approach and a phenomenology design and such allowed us to closely capture the way the phenomenon was lived by the participant parents and teachers (Creswell & Poth, 2018). It was positioned within the interpretivism paradigm, hence, we gained further depth through seeking experiences and perceptions of the participants (Alharahshen & Pius, 2020).

6. Sampling

In total, participants of this study were fifteen, and these comprised of male and female parents and teachers of learners with ASD, who were purposively sampled from four mainstream primary schools situated in the Manzini region of Eswatini.

7. Data Collection Methods

We collected data using individual semi-structured interviews, hence, the open-ended questions evoked responses which we had unanticipated (Samuels, 2019). We conducted them in venues suggested by interviewees, and for ensuring authenticity of participants' responses, we audio-recorded them (Arifin 2018). To allow teacher participants to express their perceptions free from being channelled by a sequence of questions, we also conducted a focus-group interview (Adler, Salantera & Zumstein-Shaha, 2019), and we validated the participants' interview responses by conducting document analysis (Tight, 2019), whereby, we analysed learners' classwork exercise books, workbooks, test papers, class attendance registers and marks record books.

8. Data analysis

We analysed the data using thematic analysis as postulated by Braun and Clarke (2006) whereby we: (1) familiarised ourselves with the data; (2) generated codes; (3) searched for themes; (4) reviewed the themes in relation to the codes extracted; (5) defined and named the themes; and lastly (6) generated the final report. Thematic analysis was most suitable on grounds that it allowed emergent of themes which answered the research questions (Maguire & Delahunt, 2017).

9. Ethical considerations

Ethical considerations we adhered to in this study were informed consent, by providing participants with sufficient information such that they declared their consent to participate in by endorsing their signatures in consent form reply slips which we provided to them; self-determination, by treating participants with respect and dignity through ensuring them that they had freedom to decide whether to participate or decline participation (Arifin, 2018); minimization of harm, by treating all participants fairly (Sefotho, 2018), through safeguarding them against becoming stressed while expressing their feelings during interview sessions (Arifin, 2018); anonymity, by ensuring high level of privacy of data sources through assigning pseudonyms to participants' names and schools and confidentiality of information participants divulged, by keeping all data records in a password-protected computer where only my supervisor and I had access to. Before commencement of data collection, we applied for ethical clearance from the University of Johannesburg Faculty of Education Research Ethics Committee (Creswell & Creswell, 2017), and we further sought and acquired permission from the Director of Education in Eswatini to collect data.

10. Trustworthiness of the study

Cook *et al.* (2018) view trustworthiness of a study as transparency, openness and reproducibility of evidence. In this study, we established trustworthiness through credibility, transferability, dependability and confirmability (Guba and Lincoln, 1981, cited in Huttunen and Kakkori 2020). We ensured credibility by presenting supporting

evidence of findings which were an accurate reflection of what we studied (Johnson, Adkins & Chauvin, 2020), and transferability through providing data sets and descriptions which were rich enough to enable other researchers to make judgments about the findings of this study's transferability to different contexts. We maintained dependability through instrument triangulation (Lemon & Hayes, 2020), and we achieved confirmability through checking the internal coherence of the data, findings, interpretations and recommendations.

11. Findings of the study

11.1 Parental roles boost parents' self-esteem

The life of parents of learners with ASD is characterised with low self-esteem and high affiliate stigma (Lyu *et al.*, 2021). For parents of learners with ASD to be involved in education of their children effectively, they should have an elevated self-esteem to stand negative societal attitudes which without careful consideration, would otherwise compromise their input in the education of the learners. Four out of seven parent participants mentioned that although their involvement in the education of learners with ASD was strenuous, they, however, appreciated to be part of the learners' educational journey. School C, Parent Participant 1 alluded that:

I am a teacher; I have those teacher responsibilities to do after school, like preparing for lessons, tests, and many more. I, however, understand that there is no way I can run away from my responsibility. I am ready to contribute in whichever way for her development. I am happy, that I see her almost every time.

School D, Parent Participant 1 echoed the above participant by saying that:

I am happy that I am trying and I think I get courage from being a teacher.

On the same breath, School D, Parent Participant 2 said:

I get motivated when I see her marks. It helps me psychologically.

Additionally, School B, Parent Participant 1 mentioned that:

I am comforted by the fact that I am trying.

The utilisation of terms with a positive connotation, such as 'happy' and 'comforted' underscores the unique responsibility the parents were subjected to. Hence, the finding resonates with one in a study conducted by Leadbitter *et al.* (2020) where quality time spent by the parent with their child increased attunement with the child. Though strenuous, as portrayed by the majority of parent participants in this current study, the satisfaction enabled the participants to see their involvement as aimed at facilitating academic success.

11.2. Parental role equips parents with knowledge

Mowder (2005) emphasises the need for enhancement of education of learners through strengthening school-family partnerships. Three parent participants mentioned that their involvement in education of the learners with ASD was to them also a learning curve. School A, Parent Participant 1 purported:

My role has equipped me with knowledge on autism because I never knew about autism until I had this child. I understand how a parent of a child with autism feels.

In the same vein, School C, Parent Participant 1 said:

As a teacher, I learn how I should handle parents of learners who need special education because this educates me that they have high hopes for their children. This whole situation broadens my mind to get an understanding of how a parent of the learner who needs special attention feels about our education system.

Similarly, School D, Parent Participant 1 said that:

I get knowledge and understanding of how parents of these children feel and undergo.

Although documents analysed showed very little positive academic goals attainment, the parents' responses that the various modes of involvement equipped parents with knowledge corroborates literature recorded by Marais (2020) where parents appreciated involvement because it offered them a better understanding of what was expected of them in matters of assisting the learners with ASD.

11.3 Schools offer parents insufficient support

Yaacob *et al.* (2021) highlight the significance of ensuring mental stability of parents through providing them with support. On the amount of support which the school offered to parents of learners with ASD with regards to studies, four parent participants stipulated that the support was minimal. School A, Parent Participant 1 reported that:

They tell me how we can help him. But when I check his books, I see that the content is too much for the child.

School A, Parent Participant 2 echoed School A, Parent Participant 1 by saying that:

The school tries to help us. They are always encouraging me to be closer to them. But even then, the child is still struggling.

Talking specifically on help in homeworks, School A, Parent Participant 2's response was that:

They do not give her homework, and I was about to ask why!

School B, Parent Participant 2 responded by stating that:

They give him the part they feel I should help him in. It's so challenging, but the teacher encourages me to try everything to help him with his studies.

School B, Parent Participant 1, however, seemed not to be aware of any help offered by the school. She alluded that:

I am not sure of any help at school, except tolerating her absenteeism and the pace at which she works.

To supplement the parent participants' responses, I asked teacher participants to state ways in which they supported the parents. Six out of eight teacher participants' responses demonstrated that in their quest to enhance parental involvement, they performed numerous roles. School A, Teacher Participant 1 was quoted saying:

Parents ask you to go an extra mile. And apart from being begged you take it upon yourself to avail remediation exercises. You have to provide a conducive environment, conducive meaning employing quiet a number of teaching strategies to help the learner, like, lowering the way I teach to this learner's level.

School A, Teacher Participant 2 echoed School A, Teacher Participant 1 by mentioning that: *I focus on the whole child because it sometimes happens that while I focus on the academic part there may be other developmental delays somewhere, maybe, physically. So the child may not be able to do some academic tasks unless she has developed or she is fully catered for in all spheres. I also give frequent feedback on school work, orally or using WhatsApp.*

Moreover, School C, Teacher Participant 1 posited that:

I give feedback on progress with school activities. School work is sent home once a week so that parents are aware of what is happening at school.

Additionally, School B, Teacher Participant 1 said that:

I make sure that I check progress of the learner. I also identify challenges and help on those challenges.

In response to probing, with regard to whether she provided after school teaching to accord additional activities, School B, Teacher Participant 1 explicitly stipulated that:

I don't provide any after school support because I have other commitments.

On another note, School B, Teacher Participant 2 described the support he rendered by mentioning that:

After school tutoring, at no pay. I also conduct extra classes as a means to help him to finish tasks he failed to do in class, like during testing. You know, this COVID-19 timetable is tight and it pushes the learner to write the tests even after school. So after school I continue my lesson with the learner. In fact, these learners are slow to catch up with our time table, so we sometimes even overlap to affect other teachers' periods. Worse still sometimes we write even on the following day.

School C, Teacher Participant 2 said:

Management is very particular in the way we treat such children. We are encouraged to treat them with love. So my role in supporting parents entail identifying the learners' capabilities, and training the learners to spend most time in those areas they are competent in.

Upon probing as to how they managed issues of homework, School C, Teacher Participant 2 was quoted saying:

We don't ask parents to help with studies because we are afraid that they may confuse her; we fear there might be some kind of mismatch.

Parent participants felt that schools were not providing enough support to them, while on the other hand, teachers felt that they were trying to offer parents meaningful support. Sulaimani and Gut (2019) posit that teaching of learners with ASD should be characterised by differentiated teaching strategies. This parents' dissatisfaction about support rendered by teachers is contradictory to findings from Amponsah *et al.* (2018) which revealed that parental involvement in education of learners accelerated academic achievement.

12. Conclusion

The study explored parents' perceptions towards their involvement in education of learners with ASD in Eswatini mainstream primary schools. Findings revealed that although parents' involvement was strenuous, parents were, however, happy to be part of the learners' educational journey. Parents also mentioned that their involvement broadened their scope to understand the current state of inclusive education. Furthermore, findings proved that despite that they needed a strong support system to enhance their mental health, the parents felt that schools offered them minimal support.

13. Recommendations

Parents mentioned that although being involved in the education of the learners was somehow a boost to their self-esteem, for them, juggling the multiple roles was tiresome and cumbersome. Therefore, we recommend that the Deputy Prime Minister's Office should conduct vibrant awareness campaigns in communities to inform families about the needs and impact of the presence of learners with ASD so that the entire family members can render varied forms of support to the parents, thus, create quality time for parents to navigate ways of assisting the learners in studies.

Findings revealed that although parents, as members of the micro-system level, appreciated that their involvement gave them a feel of what other parents of learners with ASD were undergoing, they were, however,

engulfed with prevalence of inadequacy of knowledge on how they could successfully improve the learners' academic performance. We, therefore, recommend that the Ministry of Education and Training should deploy full-time teacher-counsellors to facilitate provision of psychoeducation to assist parents acquire systematic, crucial information on ASD, and relevant treatment services to enhance coping for both the learners and their parents (Visser & Moleko, 2019). A vibrant multi-disciplinary team of ASD experts should as well be roped in to share salient strategies on how home environments could be modified to minimise disruptive aggressive behavioural problems.

The Draft Inclusive Education Policy views robust pre- and in-service training as a vital mechanism through which inclusive education can be successfully implemented (Ministry of Education and Training, 2008). In light of the finding where parent participants viewed teachers' support towards their involvement in learners' studies as insufficient, we recommend that the National Curriculum Centre, should consider developing a comprehensive ASD-specific curriculum which should guide teacher training institutions to specifically equip aspiring teachers with ample relevant skills to mitigate the current state of parents and learners with ASD in mainstream primary schools. Moreover, the In-service Education and Training department should conduct frequent robust workshops to intensively capacitate in-service teachers with imperative accommodative inclusionary strategies to make school and out of school environment welcoming to parental involvement.

While national policies should be tailor-made to suit consumers, their formulation is, however, greatly influenced by the ideologies of legislators who hold top management positions. In this regard, we recommend that the Ministry of Education and Training, should craft a comprehensive independent policy to clearly outline guidelines on how parents of learners with special education needs should be involved in educating the learners. Schools can then use that policy to draw their own policies, to as well outline areas in which parents can volunteer.

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